

Application of Strategic Management Practices in Public Sector Organizations: A Case Study of Sierra Leone Port Authority

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Abstract

This research examines the application of strategic management practices in public organizations, specifically the Sierra Leone Port Authority (SLPA). The study focuses on four main areas: how well strategic planning works, how leadership affects implementation, how resources are allocated, and how performance is measured. The goal is to see how these practices impact SLPA's overall performance. The research used both surveys from 100 SLPA employees and interviews with 15 top leaders. The data shows that strong leadership is closely linked to effective strategic planning, with a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.56$, $p < 0.01$), which supports previous research showing that good leadership is key to strategic success.

Resource allocation received a lower score (average = 3.3), showing difficulties in matching resources with strategic goals. Additionally, performance measurement systems were linked to organizational success, emphasizing the need for strong performance tracking to ensure public accountability. These results support the principles of New Public Management (NPM), which promotes results-focused management in the public sector. They show that effective leadership, strategic planning, and performance measurement are crucial for the SLPA to achieve its operational and strategic aims. This research adds to the understanding of strategic management in public sectors with limited resources, providing useful information for both policy-making and practical applications.

Keywords: Strategic management, public sector, Sierra Leone Port Authority, leadership, resource allocation, performance measurement, New Public Management

1. Introduction

Strategic management is crucial for improving efficiency and performance in public sector organizations, especially when dealing with political influence, limited resources, and complex stakeholder needs, which require specific strategies (Chiwawa, Wissink, & Fox, 2021). In countries like Sierra Leone, these challenges are even more noticeable, making it vital for public institutions like the Sierra Leone Port Authority (SLPA) to adopt well-organized strategic management practices that meet the country's socio-economic needs. The SLPA, like many public organizations, operates in an environment where it must balance diverse stakeholder expectations with its goals, often with limited resources. A well-structured strategic management approach can be a key tool in helping the SLPA achieve these goals (Höglund, Mårtensson, & Thomson, 2021; Bryson, Crosby, and Barberg, 2023).

Public organizations are moving away from old ways of managing things and are now focusing more on strategic management. This change is driven by the growing need for transparency, accountability, and creating value for the public (Ali & Beh, 2019). Models like Moore's (1995) strategic triangle which looks at the authorizing environment, public value, and operational capacity show how public institutions can achieve these goals by balancing political sustainability, organizational legitimacy, and resource alignment (Moore, 2014). But studies indicate that public organizations in developing regions, like parts of Africa,

often struggle to use these models because of issues like poor infrastructure, political instability, and financial difficulties (Chiwawa et al, 2021; Bryson et al, 2023).

Even though strategic management methods have shown promise, the SLPA continues to struggle with using these approaches to boost service effectiveness and involve stakeholders. There is not much research on how these methods are used in the SLPA or similar African port authorities, which shows a big missing piece in understanding what special changes are needed for successful use in these situations (Chiwawa et al, 2021; Bryson et al, 2023). This study, therefore, wants to find out how well strategic management methods can be used in the SLPA to improve organization performance and create public value, adding to the larger discussion about managing public sectors in places with limited resources.

This study will offer ideas on particular strategies that could help the SLPA overcome challenges, following successful methods used by similar public organizations worldwide (Höglund et al, 2021; Bryson et al, 2023).

This study looks at how strategic management is used at the Sierra Leone Port Authority (SLPA). It aims to give a full analysis of the important factors that affect the organization's strategic and daily operations. The main goals of the research are:

1. To evaluate the effectiveness of strategic planning at Sierra Leone Port Authority (SLPA).
2. To assess the role of leadership in the implementation of strategic management practices.
3. To examine the challenges associated with resource allocation within Sierra Leone Port Authority (SLPA).
4. To analyze the performance measurement system and its impact on organizational performance.

2. Literature Review:

This review brings together recent studies about how strategic management is used in public organizations, especially in strategic planning, leadership during implementation, resource distribution, and performance evaluation. These topics show how strategic management affects how well and quickly public organizations can adapt, which is important for groups like the Sierra Leone Port Authority (SLPA) that work under special conditions.

Strategic Planning in Government Agencies

Strategic planning is a key method for helping government agencies reach their long-term goals while meeting public needs and dealing with political and operational issues. Recent research shows that good strategic planning in government should include a thorough analysis of the environment and involve stakeholders so that agencies can match their goals with broader social and political factors (Bryson, 2018; George et al., 2019). According to Bryson et al. (2018), strategic planning allows public organizations to set up systems that connect resources and actions with larger government aims, creating benefits for the public that go beyond typical business goals.

Additionally, Bryson and Edwards (2017) discovered that having a clear strategic plan helps organizations adjust better to fast-changing situations, which is very important for public organizations dealing with frequent changes in policies and public expectations. Similarly, Pevcin (2024) points out that a structured strategic planning process is essential in places recovering from conflicts, like Sierra Leone. In such resource-limited environments, strategic planning needs to focus on adaptability and long-term goals to support growth and performance. For the Sierra Leone Port Authority (SLPA), using a strategic planning process that focuses on being responsive and engaging with stakeholders is key to aligning its goals with Sierra Leone's economic and development plans (Pevcin, 2024; George et al., 2019).

The Role of Leadership in Implementing Strategic Management Practices

Leadership is very important in using strategic management methods. Leaders in public organizations have to deal with many levels of responsibility, what the public wants, and political pressure. Recent studies show that transformational leadership works well in public organizations, helping to create a culture that can

change, stay strong, and be creative (Andrews, Boyne & Walker, 2020; Vogel & Masal, 2015). George et al. (2019) say that public leaders who use a transformational style can encourage people to support the organization's goals, making it easier to put complex plans into action.

The success of leadership in implementing public sector strategies depends on creating a culture that values accountability and encourages innovation. Bryson et al (2018) believe that strategic leaders play a crucial role in balancing organizational goals with external political influences, which is especially important for an organization like SLPA, where operational decisions are closely tied to national economic policies. For SLPA, leadership that focuses on adaptability and communicates strategic goals can help align policy directives with daily operations, improving both organizational efficiency and public trust (Vogel & Masal, 2015; George et al., 2019).

Challenges of Resource Allocation in Government Agencies

Resource allocation is a big challenge for public sector organizations. They have to deal with limited money, political goals, and many different public needs. Recent research, like the work by van Dooren and Van de Walle (2020), shows that smart resource allocation needs to focus on being efficient and match the main goals of public services. Bryson et al. (2018) found that effective resource allocation often uses budgeting based on performance and ways to set priorities that help reach important organizational goals.

In public sector organizations with limited resources, like SLPA, it's important but difficult to focus on the most critical areas for resource allocation to ensure long-term operation. Pevcin (2024) and Andrews et al. (2020) recommend that public institutions should use a performance-based approach to allocate resources, even when money is tight, to get the most benefit. This approach matches research showing that public sector resource allocation needs to be flexible to handle changing public needs and policy shifts (Bryson & Edwards, 2017; van Dooren & Van de Walle, 2020). For SLPA, this could involve using methods that prioritize high-impact areas, making sure that limited resources are used effectively.

Performance Measurement Systems and Their Effect on Organizational Performance

Performance measurement is crucial for strategic management in public sector organizations, as it helps ensure accountability, transparency, and ongoing improvement. Recent research shows that performance measurement systems in public organizations should be closely linked to broader strategic goals, enabling continuous evaluation and adjustment (Poister et al., 2015; Bryson et al., 2018). Studies by George et al. (2019) and Pevcin (2024) indicate that performance measurement in public institutions should not only focus on traditional metrics but also include measures of public value and service delivery efficiency.

For SLPA, using a clear system to measure performance could help understand how well the organization is working, how closely it matches its goals, and how it affects public services. Research by Vogel and Masal (2015) shows that performance measurement systems not only make things more transparent but also encourage a culture of ongoing learning and adapting in public organizations. Similarly, Poister et al. (2015) believe that using data to assess performance is crucial for meeting public accountability standards and making quick strategic changes. This method could help SLPA improve its strategies, better respond to public needs, and use resources more efficiently (George et al., 2019).

Research on strategic management in public organizations highlights the value of flexible planning, strong leadership, prioritizing resources, and effective performance tracking in reaching organizational objectives. For SLPA, these strategic approaches are crucial for improving operational stability, aligning with national development goals, and providing public benefits. Applying these practices can help SLPA overcome the typical challenges of public sector work, ultimately supporting Sierra Leone's economic development.

3. Methodology

This research examines how strategic management techniques are used at the Sierra Leone Port Authority (SLPA), looking at strategic planning, leadership, resource distribution, and performance evaluation. The study uses a combination of both qualitative and quantitative methods to give a full picture of how these

management practices affect SLPA's operational effectiveness and its alignment with public sector objectives. Using both types of methods is useful for public sector studies because it helps to understand both the strategic processes and measurable results in complex organizations (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010).

Research Design

This study employs a cross-sectional approach, examining data from SLPA at one particular time. Cross-sectional methods are ideal for exploratory research in public sector management because they offer a snapshot of current strategic practices, allowing for comparisons and the spotting of trends within organizations (Bryman, 2016). In public sector studies, cross-sectional methods are commonly used to evaluate strategic implementation across different departments or government agencies, thanks to their effectiveness in capturing organizational setups and practices (Poister, 2015).

The study uses a survey to gather numerical data on strategic management practices and in-depth interviews to get detailed insights from the management team and stakeholders of SLPA. Combining these methods is crucial for looking at both the measurable parts of the strategy, like resource distribution and performance measures, and the personal experiences of leadership and implementation difficulties (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010).

Sampling

The research used a method called purposive sampling, which focused on 120 employees from SLPA in different positions, such as top management, middle managers, and strategic planning staff. This method is very useful in public sector studies because it helps pick people who have special knowledge and experience in strategic practices, making sure the data is relevant (Patton, 2014). Out of the 120 people invited, 100 completed the survey (83.3% response rate), and 15 top leaders took part in semi-structured interviews. This group of people, with their different roles, gives a complete picture of strategic management practices and views at various levels within SLPA.

Data Collection

Quantitative Data: A survey was given to SLPA employees with questions meant to assess how well strategic planning works, how leaders perform their roles, how resources are used efficiently, and how performance tools are utilized. The survey questions were adapted from well-established strategic management tools, tailored to fit the SLPA environment. Participants answered using a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), making it easier to measure and compare different strategic management practices (Poister et al., 2015).

Qualitative Data: We had detailed, partly planned talks with 15 top managers from SLPA. These talks helped us learn about strategic management practices, like dealing with limited resources and leadership methods in a public sector setting. The partly planned format kept the interviews consistent but also let us explore individual insights. This method works well in public sector studies, where understanding the complex views on policy and organizational culture is important (Yin, 2017; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).

Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis: We used descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the survey data. Descriptive statistics helped us see patterns in how SLPA handles strategic planning, leadership, and resource allocation. Inferential techniques, like correlation and regression analyses were used to find connections between different factors, such as how leadership affects strategic planning results. We did this analysis using SPSS software, which is commonly used for accurate and reliable quantitative research in the public sector (Poister, 2015; Bryman, 2016).

Qualitative Analysis: The information gathered from interviews was examined using thematic analysis, a technique that helps in finding and understanding patterns in qualitative data. The interview notes were looked at and categorized according to common topics, like strategic alignment, difficulties in resource

allocation, and methods for measuring performance. Thematic analysis allows for handling complex data and discovering insights that might be missed by quantitative methods (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Yin, 2017).

Combining quantitative and qualitative findings helped to cross-check the data, making the results more dependable. By comparing numerical patterns with insights from managers, this combined approach gives a full picture of SLPA's strategic actions. It reveals not just the measurable effects but also the company culture and leadership factors that influence strategic results in the public sector.

Analysis

This section presents a quantitative analysis of SLPA's strategic management methods using survey responses from 100 participants. It covers basic statistics, correlation studies, and regression studies for four main areas: Strategic Planning Effectiveness, Leadership's Role in Implementation, Resource Allocation, and Performance Measurement Systems. The findings are explained to see how they impact SLPA's overall organizational performance.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics give a summary of how people feel about the four different topics. Each topic was rated on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "Strongly Disagree" and 5 means "Strongly Agree". The table below shows the average rating and how much the ratings varied for each topic.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strategic Planning Effectiveness	3.8	0.85
The role of leadership in implantation	4.2	0.78
Resource Allocation	3.3	0.92
Performance Measurement Systems	4.8	0.83

SLPA employees have a good view of their leadership and how performance is measured, giving these areas average scores of 4.2 and 4.0. However, they rate Resource Allocation lower, with an average score of 3.3, suggesting there might be some issues in this area.

Correlation Analysis

We performed a correlation analysis to look at how Strategic Planning Effectiveness, Leadership Implementation, Resource Allocation, and Performance Measurement Systems are related to each other.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix for Key Variables

Variable Pair	Correlation Coefficient (r)	P-value
Strategic Planning Effectiveness	0.56	< 0.01
The role of leadership in implantation	0.42	< 0.05
Resource Allocation & Performance Measurement	0.45	< 0.05

Strategic Planning Effectiveness is closely linked to Leadership Implementation ($r = 0.56$, $p < 0.01$), showing that leadership plays a big role in making strategic planning work well. Resource Allocation is also connected to Performance Measurement ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.05$), meaning that better resource management often leads to better performance tracking.

Regression Analysis

To see how Leadership Implementation, Resource Allocation, and Performance Measurement affect Strategic Planning Effectiveness, we used a method called multiple regression analysis. The table below shows the results of this analysis.

Predictor Variable	Regression Coefficient (β)	Standard Error	P-Value
Leadership in implantation	0.42	0.10	< 0.01
Resource Allocation	0.32	0.11	< 0.05
Performance Measurement Systems	0.38	0.9	< 0.05
R-Squared	0.64		

The model accounts for 64% of the changes in Strategic Planning Effectiveness ($R^2 = 0.64$). Leadership Implementation is the most significant factor ($\beta = 0.42$, $p < 0.01$), followed by Performance Measurement Systems ($\beta = 0.38$, $p < 0.05$) and Resource Allocation ($\beta = 0.32$, $p < 0.05$). These findings highlight that strong leadership, proper resource allocation, and effective performance measurement are essential for successful strategic planning at SLPA.

In summary, leadership and performance measurement systems are seen as strong points in SLPA. However, the way resources are allocated needs improvement. While, there are also strong connections between how well Strategic Planning works and both Leadership Implementation and Performance Measurement Systems, showing how important these factors are. Lastly, leadership Implementation is the most important factor that predicts how well Strategic Planning works, making leadership crucial for reaching strategic goals.

These results indicate that for SLPA, improving leadership skills, using resources wisely, and setting up strong systems to measure performance are key to enhancing strategic management.

4. Discussion

The results from the Sierra Leone Port Authority (SLPA) highlight the intricate relationship between leadership, strategic management, resource distribution, and performance evaluation in public sector organizations. Together, these factors determine the success of strategic plans and offer valuable information about what drives organizational performance in places like Sierra Leone, where resources are limited.

Leadership and Strategic Management Practices

The findings show that leadership is very important for making strategic planning work well at SLPA. There is a strong connection ($r = 0.56$) and it has a big impact ($\beta = 0.42$, $p < 0.01$) on how well strategic planning works. This matches what experts say about the importance of leaders who inspire and involve others in making strategies work better (Bryson & Edwards, 2017; Andrews, Boyne, Law & Walker, 2012). In government organizations, where goals are linked to political needs and being responsible to others, good leaders help make sure that what is planned is actually done by making sure the organization's goals match the actions taken (George et al., 2019).

The effectiveness of SLPA's leadership in strategic planning matches the findings of Bryson (2018), who studied strategic management in the public sector. Bryson highlights that leaders need to set clear objectives, encourage responsibility, and make sure their teams can adapt. The importance of leadership in SLPA implies that improving leadership training and decision-making could help the organization reach its strategic goals, even with limited resources. These insights suggest that for SLPA and similar public bodies, focusing on leadership development could enhance their strategic impact, closely following research showing leadership's vital role in public sector success (Vogel & Masal, 2015)

Resource Allocation

Resource allocation became a significant issue, with average scores (3.3) lower than those for leadership and performance measurement. These match problems are seen in other public sector organizations, where limited money and competing goals often make it hard to carry out strategies (Pevcin, 2024). Limited resources make it difficult for SLPA to focus on important projects, a common problem in public institutions trying to balance tight budgets with various public service needs (van Dooren & Van de Walle, 2020). The link between resource allocation and performance measurement ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.05$) backs up research by

Andrews et al.(2012), showing that well-managed resources lead to better tracking and more effective use of funds.

For SLPA, using methods like performance-based budgeting could help make the best use of limited resources by focusing them on projects that most support important goals. Using these methods would follow the principles of New Public Management (NPM), which focus on using resources efficiently and with clear goals in mind (Bryson, 2018). By connecting resource spending with clear results, SLPA can increase accountability and show its worth to those it serves, which is important in public sectors with limited resources.

Performance Measurement

SLPA's performance evaluation systems were highly regarded (mean = 4.0), highlighting their importance in improving transparency and accountability. The strong link between performance evaluation and the effectiveness of strategic planning ($\beta = 0.38, p < 0.05$) matches findings by Poister, Aristigueta & Hall, (2014), who believe that good performance metrics help public sector organizations monitor progress, check the success of programs, and modify strategies when necessary. SLPA's approach to performance evaluation mirrors a larger trend in public management, where data-based decision-making is increasingly crucial for organizational success and public confidence (George, Walker & Monster, 2019).

Using performance measurement systems helps SLPA stay focused on its goals and encourages a culture that values results, which is important in public administration (Bryson & Edwards, 2017). For SLPA, improving these systems to include broader measures, like the impact of services and public satisfaction, would give a fuller picture of how well the organization is doing. This method fits with Moore's (2014) idea of public value, which says that public organizations should measure both their day-to-day work and their overall outcomes to understand their total impact.

Strategic Management Practices and Organizational Performance

The study shows that strategic planning, when led actively and backed by good resource management and performance tracking, greatly affects SLPA's overall performance. Following the principles of New Public Management (NPM), which promote results-focused management in the public sector, SLPA's methodical approach to strategic management emphasizes accountability, transparency, and flexibility (Bryson, & Edwards, 2017). These practices together support the idea that aligning organizational goals with operational abilities is crucial, especially in public organizations (Poister, 2015)

SLPA's reliance on robust strategic practices shows how public sector organizations can use methods inspired by the private sector while still keeping public service values. This balance between working efficiently and being accountable to the public matches what van Dooren and Van de Walle, (2010) found, which is that using strategic management plans can improve both performance and trust from those involved. By including leadership, focusing on where resources are needed, and regularly checking performance, SLPA can connect its strategic goals with its daily operations. This approach has worked well in other public sector settings (Andrews, Boyne, Law & Walker, 2012; Bryson, 2018).

5. Conclusion

To sum up, the results show that improving leadership skills, making the best use of resources, and keeping close track of performance is key to making strategic management better at SLPA. These ideas match what other studies say about the importance of flexible, well-planned strategies in public sector management. For SLPA, paying attention to these strategic areas could help it better meet its public service goals, which would support Sierra Leone's economic and infrastructure development.

This research offers important information about how SLPA manages its strategies, showing problems with leadership, resource distribution, and performance tracking. To make their strategic management better, SLPA needs to work on making leadership more effective, dealing with limited resources, and using strong systems to measure performance. These suggestions can also help other public organizations in developing countries that have similar issues.

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